

FAMILIARITY AND MANIFESTATIONS OF SK REFORM ACT OF 2015 AMONG ‘GEN Z’ SK FEDERATION MEMBERS IN BAIS CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the extent of familiarity with and the manifestations of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Reform Act of 2015 among Generation Z SK Federation Members in Bais City, Negros Oriental. Grounded in Boone et al. (1977) Social Learning Theory and Rappaport’s Community Empowerment Theory, the research examines how knowledge of the reform’s key provisions—expanded age bracket, mandatory leadership training, anti-dynasty clause, creation of the Local Youth Development Council (LYDC), and financial independence—translates into leadership practices such as decision-making, community engagement, accountability, and motivation. Using a descriptive-correlational research design and census sampling method, data were gathered through a validated survey instrument administered to all 267 Gen Z SK members in Bais City. Statistical analysis revealed that respondents demonstrated a very high level of familiarity with the SK Reform Act and a correspondingly strong manifestation of leadership perspectives. Significant positive correlations were found between familiarity with the law and key leadership dimensions, particularly decision-making, community involvement, role perception, and motivation. The study concludes that increased awareness of the SK Reform Act significantly enhances youth leadership performance, highlighting the importance of structured education, inclusive policies, and continued training. The findings serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, educators, and local government units aiming to empower youth through governance and civic engagement.

Keywords: *Generation Z; Sangguniang Kabataan; SK Reform Act of 2015; youth empowerment; youth leader*

INTRODUCTION

There is a rising recognition globally of the role of young people, particularly Generation Z, in their role in addressing complex societal challenges. They are proactively engaged in various national and local socio-political issues (Calawa et al., 2023) making them an integral part of global development. The youth contribute a lot to solving issues such as environmental sustainability and social justice by using their unique perspectives and knowledge. According to Apollo and Mbah (2022), their capacity for innovation enables them to address community challenges effectively, making them indispensable in creating inclusive and long-term solutions for a rapidly changing world. Their role in policy-making and program development is essential to harness their potential for impactful change around the world.

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) serves as a grassroots organization for youth leadership development and community participation. It has the goal of developing mentorship and governance skills among the young (Pasicaran-Escleto et al., 2024). However, there are specific challenges to the program, including inefficiency, corruption, and diminished trust. Republic Act 10742 also known as 2015 SK Reform Act aims to address these issues by introducing measures to improve accountability and representation. This mandate increased accountability and effectiveness of youth leadership, especially on financial transparency, management of funds, and capacity to plan and implement beneficial programs (Palangdao et al., 2023; Palomares et al., 2023).

Despite these reforms, barriers to youth participation, such as lack of awareness and time constraints, persist. Furthermore, trust in the SK has weakened due to incidents of abuse and governance failures (Flores et al., 2022). Critics, including Castillo et al. (2024), have even proposed the abolition of the SK, citing its ineffectiveness and ethical lapses. This situation underscores the need for deeper exploration into its potential to empower the youth and their ability to lead.

Nevertheless, there is a lack of research exploring the specific impact of the SK Reform Act of 2015 in addressing issues within the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK). Unlike earlier studies that focus on the organization's challenges, this research examines how the reform act fosters youth engagement, improves accountability, and rebuilds trust. By analyzing its key provisions and practical effects, the study aims to understand how these reforms influence the leadership practices of Gen Z SK members in Bais City and reshape the SK's role in driving community development.

With that being said, the significance of this study focuses on understanding how the 2015 SK Reform Act has worked to improve the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) and suggests practical ways to update youth programs. The results of this paper could help the government and other concerned organizations provide better support for reforms that

respond to the evolving needs of today's youth. Furthermore, by promoting youth participation in leadership, governance, and civic engagement, this study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) particularly SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2023). It highlights the importance of investing in the skills, leadership capacity, and civic competencies of young people as a pathway to fostering inclusive economic development, productive employment, and sustainable youth empowerment in the country. Strengthening the role of youth in governance builds a foundation for future leaders who are well-equipped to contribute meaningfully to national growth. Through active involvement in programs like SK, young individuals can develop relevant skills, expand their networks, and prepare for decent and fulfilling work in the future.

METHODOLOGY

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate how the SK Reform Act of 2015 influences the leadership perspectives of the 'Gen Z' members of the SK Federation in Bais City. Specifically, the study sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the 'Gen Z' SK Federation Members in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex,
 - 1.3 educational attainment;
 - 1.4 number of mandatory trainings; and
 - 1.5 length of service in SK?
2. To what extent is the familiarity of the respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 expanded age bracket;
 - 2.2 mandatory leadership training;
 - 2.3 anti-dynasty provision;
 - 2.4 creation of a Local Youth Development Council (LYDC);
 - 2.5 financial independence?
3. To what extent does the SK Reform Act manifest the leadership perspectives of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 3.1 decision-making and problem solving;
 - 3.2 community engagement;
 - 3.3 perception of roles and responsibilities;
 - 3.4 motivation and commitment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of the respondents' familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015 and the extent of its manifestations in their leadership perspectives?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the following:
 - 5.1 extent of familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015; and

5.2 extent of manifestations in their leadership perspectives?

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive-correlational approach, to examine the impact of the SK Reform Act of 2015 on the leadership perspectives of 'Gen Z' members of the SK Federation in Bais City. The descriptive aspect of the study aimed to provide an accurate account of the respondents' familiarity with the SK Reform Act and their leadership perspectives. The correlational component explored the relationships between the level of familiarity with the SK Reform Act and the manifestation of leadership skills, determining how these factors are connected. Data was gathered through surveys using structured questionnaires, and statistical analyses were employed to assess the strength and direction of the relationships between the variables.

Research Environment

Bais City is a city in the Philippines' Negros Oriental province, and is known for its natural attractions and fertile soil. Bais City has a land area of 319.64 square kilometers and is made up of 35 barangays. The City of Bais constitutes a political body corporate and as such is endowed with the attribute of perpetual succession and possessed of the powers which pertain to a municipal corporation. Upon observation, the community has numbers of Euphorbia in the vicinity wherein uses by the residence in any purposes 'Gen Z' SK Federation that currently leads the group of youth. It has been perceived that the Gen Z SK Federation has poor performance on their leadership perspective and awareness on SK Reform Act of 2015. This scenario allows the researchers to select the area and conduct survey to aid the gap of the study.

Research Respondents

This study focused on 267 'Gen Z' members of the SK Federation in Bais City, selected using the sampling technique. In this method, sampling involved collecting data from every individual in the population of interest. In this study, the population consisted of all 'Gen Z' SK members within a municipality. Since the total population size was small and accessible, sampling was chosen to ensure comprehensive representation and to eliminate sampling bias. Sampling was used to ensure that the perspectives of all SK members were captured, providing a comprehensive understanding of the research problem. Data collection involved administering a survey to all SK members in Bais City, with efforts made to ensure full participation. This approach eliminated sampling bias and provided a complete dataset for analysis.

To qualify as participants in this study, individuals had to meet the following inclusion criteria:

1. Must be a current member of the SK Federation in Bais City.
2. Must belong to Generation Z (born between 1997 and 2012)

3. Must have voluntarily agreed to participate in the study and provided informed consent.

Research Instruments

The researcher utilized primary data collected directly from the respondents through a survey. This approach provided real-time, relevant data that aligned with the study's objectives. The data was gathered using a questionnaire, with items categorized to address the specific goals of the study.

Part I of the questionnaire had the disclosure statement, which explains the purpose of the study and provides important details about the participants' involvement. This statement ensured that respondents understand their role in the research and their rights as participants. It also assured them that their answers will be handled carefully and kept private. This section focused as well on the profile of the 'Gen Z' SK Federation members, gathering information on their age, sex, educational attainment, number of trainings, and length of service in the SK. Part II will assess the respondents' familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015, focusing on key aspects such as the expanded age bracket, mandatory leadership training, the anti-dynasty provision, the creation of a Local Youth Development Council (LYDC), and financial independence. Part III will explore how the provisions of the SK Reform Act of 2015 manifested in the leadership perspectives of the respondents. Part IV also assess the manifestations of SK Reform Act 2015 on 'Gen Z' Member's decision-making and problem-solving skills, community engagement skills, perception of roles and responsibilities and motivation and commitment skills.

The entire questionnaire was validated by at least 3 professors who are master's degree holders and who are into research undertakings. A dry run would also be performed to ensure item reliability. The 'Gen Z' SK Federation members will serve as respondents. The Cronbach's alpha test will be used to assess the items' reliability. This test would be regarded as the most appropriate type for survey research where questions would not be rated as correct or incorrect and where each item may have several answers (Stigler et al., 2020). This would be calculated to check the items' internal consistency reliability. It is a measure of how closely all of the variables on the scale are related to one another, and its theoretical value ranges from 0 to 1. Higher alpha values are preferable, while 0.70 is regarded acceptable. This data collection approach ensure that the information gathered would be comprehensive and relevant, addressing the research questions outlined in the study. The items in the questionnaire would be designed to capture the key variables of interest, offering a clear understanding of the relationship between the respondents' familiarity with the law and their leadership practices.

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Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

The researchers followed a clear process to gather the data and information needed for the study. After the design hearing, the researcher integrated all the corrections and suggestions from the panel members. First, the researcher sent a letter to the SK Federation President asking for permission to conduct the study and collect data among its 'Gen Z' SK Federation members. During the distribution, the researcher explained the purpose and importance of the research.

Once the target population was identified, the researchers sent a written request for permission to the local management where the study would take place. They also ensured that ethical practices were followed in collecting the data. After receiving approval, the survey was administered to the 'Gen Z' SK Federation members. These respondents answered the structured questionnaires based on their own opinions and experiences. Once the researchers collected the responses, they processed and interpreted the data to find patterns and insights. The results were then tallied using MS Excel/Spreadsheet software. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and correlational approaches, which helped determine the results of the study. Lastly, the conclusions and summary of findings were written.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical research principles to ensure the integrity of the research process and the protection of participants' rights. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their involvement. Participants were provided with clear information about the purpose of the study, their role in the research, and the potential benefits and risks associated with their participation.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1. Profile of the 'Gen Z' SK Federation Members

Category	Classification	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age	18–19	15	5.62
	20–21	85	31.84
	22–23	104	38.95
	≥24	63	23.59
Sex	Male	134	50.19
	Female	133	49.81
Educational Attainment	High School Graduate	49	18.35
	College Undergraduate	154	57.68

	College Graduate	64	23.97
No. of Mandatory Trainings	0	37	13.86
	1	153	57.30
	2	46	17.23
	3	19	7.12
	≥4	12	4.49
Length of Service (Years)	1	127	47.57
	2	128	47.94
	≥3	12	4.49

This section presents the demographic characteristics of the SK Federation members in Bais City, including their age, sex, educational attainment, participation in mandatory trainings, and length of service. Understanding these variables provides essential context for interpreting their leadership perspectives and familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015.

Table 1 reveals that the majority of respondents are aged 22 to 23 years old (38.95%), followed by those aged 20 to 21 (31.84%), while the least represented group is 18 to 19 years old (5.62%). This distribution suggests that the SK Federation is predominantly composed of older Gen Z members, aligning with the expanded age range under the SK Reform Act of 2015. The finding is like Akira et al. (2024) which established that older youth are serving the organization. It can be deduced that they are more likely to engage in governance due to greater civic awareness. In terms of gender, the data shows nearly equal representation, with males constituting 50.19% and females 49.81%, reflecting a high level of gender inclusivity within the SK Federation. As noted by Leah Filho et al. (2022), a successful implementation of gender equality can be achieved when policies raised awareness on gender equality contribution.

Respondents also demonstrated a diverse range of academic backgrounds: the majority are college undergraduates (57.68%), followed by college graduates (23.97%) and high school graduates (18.35%). This emphasizes the importance of engaging youth from various educational levels, as educational attainment is linked to enhanced civic engagement and leadership skills (Shukri et al., 2025). However, Table 1 also highlights limited exposure to mandatory training: 57.30% attended only one session, while 13.86% received none. This is concerning given the SK Reform Act's requirement for leadership training for elected officials; insufficient training, as suggested by Madrid et al. (2020), may hinder effective governance.

Finally, regarding length of service, most SK members have served for one (47.57%) or two years (47.94%), with only 4.49% having served three or more years. This pattern suggests that many members are still in the early stages of their leadership development. The Leadership Identity Development (LID) model supports the view that leadership

capacity evolves with continued exposure, mentorship, and practical experience (Tackett et al., 2022).

Table 2. Extent Familiarity of the Respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of Expanded Age Bracket (n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	EoF
1. Individuals aged 15 to 30 years old are eligible to vote for SK.	4.75	VH
2. Individuals aged 18 to 24 years old are qualified to run for SK.	4.73	VH
3. I am aware of the procedures to register as voter.	4.71	VH
4. Having on the right age to vote enables me to fulfill my political and civil rights.	4.70	VH
5. I knew the age bracket of voters and qualified age for SK.	4.66	VH
Composite	4.71	VH

Legend: Scale	Extent of Familiarity (EoF)
4.21 – 5.00	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)

Table 2 presents the extent of familiarity of the respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of the expanded age bracket. The results show a composite mean of 4.71, which falls under the “Very High” interpretation. This indicates that the respondents are highly knowledgeable about the legal age qualifications for voting and candidacy in the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) system.

A significant number of respondents demonstrated strong awareness that individuals aged 15 to 30 years old are eligible to vote for SK, which earned the highest \bar{x} score of 4.75. This reflects an encouraging trend in youth civic awareness, where young people understand their right to participate in local elections. This level of familiarity strengthens the foundation for democratic involvement and demonstrate participants political awareness. As argued by Chen and Madni (2024), people’s political awareness enhances their political engagement which promotes democratic involvement. Young voters’ civic awareness directly translates to active and meaningful participation in democratic processes.

Similarly, a high \bar{x} score of 4.73 was recorded for the item recognizing that individuals aged 18 to 24 years old are qualified to run for SK positions. This result shows that young leaders are well-informed about their eligibility to hold office under the reformed system. The adjustment in the candidacy age bracket was a major provision of the SK Reform Act, aimed at ensuring that elected youth leaders possess sufficient maturity and the capacity to be held legally responsible for their actions. The participants awareness on the age bracket fosters their confidence and accountability in leading which, according to Hornyak et al. (2022) offers opportunities benefitting the individual and the organization they are involved.

Moreover, respondents also indicated a high level of understanding of the procedures to register as a voter, with a \bar{x} of 4.71. This suggests that the youth not only know their eligibility but are also aware of the processes needed to exercise their right to vote. Such procedural knowledge is essential to actual civic engagement. As revealed by Heroux-Legault (2023), political knowledge including its procedures led to wise voting decisions. The author added that informed voters utilize spatial reasoning in exercising their civil rights. It can therefore be deduced that access to information about registration and election procedures empowers young citizens to participate meaningfully in governance. Another key finding is the 4.70 \bar{x} response to the statement that having the right age to vote enables one to fulfill political and civil rights. This highlights that many youth respondents do not see voting merely as a civic duty, but as a vital right tied to their identity as active citizens. Amante et al. (2024) stresses that contribution of Filipino youth in changing the country's social and political landscape, especially that they comprised one-third of voters in the 2019 and 2022 elections.

Lastly, the \bar{x} of 4.66 for knowing both the age bracket of voters and the qualified age to run for SK further supports the overall result. Respondents appear well-versed in the key qualifications outlined in the SK Reform Act, showing that legal information has effectively reached the youth sector. This is significant, as proper awareness of legal frameworks contributes to well-informed participation and reduces the risk of disqualification or misuse of authority.

Table 3. Extent Familiarity of the Respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of Mandatory Leadership Training (n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	EoF
1. The purpose of the leadership trainings is emphasizing the role of the youth in nation-building and molding them to become better citizens.	4.73	VH
2. SK officials has to undergo mandatory leadership training as one of the key reforms and requirement for all elected SK Officials.	4.72	VH
3. Training equips SK officials with the knowledge and skills needed to be effective youth leaders.	4.70	VH
4. The mandatory training allows me to mold to a strong leader for youth.	4.70	VH
5. The mandatory trainings provide the newly elected SK officials with a comprehensive understanding of their roles and responsibilities, enabling them to serve their communities more efficiently.	4.69	VH
Composite	4.71	VH

Legend: Scale	Extent of Familiarity (EoF)
4.21 – 5.00	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)

Table 3 presents the extent of familiarity of the respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of Mandatory Leadership Training, with a composite \bar{x} of 4.71, interpreted as “Very High.” This result suggests that youth leaders possess a strong understanding of the purpose and significance of the required leadership training mandated by law for all elected SK officials.

The highest-rated indicator, with a \bar{x} of 4.73, shows that respondents clearly recognize that the purpose of leadership training is to emphasize the role of the youth in nation-building and to mold them into better citizens. This reflects a deep appreciation for the civic value and transformative nature of these trainings. According to Pasicaran-Escleto et al. (2024) training prepares young leaders and empowers them to take an active role in local governance. It also allows them to gain experiences to effectively function in their respective responsibilities.

Closely following with a \bar{x} of 4.72, respondents affirmed that undergoing mandatory leadership training is a key reform and requirement for all elected SK officials. This awareness aligns with the implementation of Republic Act No. 10742, which institutionalized pre-assumption training to ensure that officials are prepared before assuming office. Madrid et al. (2020) emphasize that this reform was introduced to prevent unpreparedness in public office and promote good governance among youth leaders from the outset.

Respondents also strongly agreed, with a \bar{x} of 4.70, that training equips SK officials with the necessary knowledge and skills to be effective youth leaders. This indicates that they see these programs not merely as requirements, but as valuable tools for personal development. Supporting this, the Global Youth Council stresses that effective training should involve practical, strategic, and values-based components to ensure young leaders can implement community programs successfully.

Another indicator, with a \bar{x} of 4.70, reflects the view that mandatory training molds young people into strong leaders for the youth sector. This finding suggests that the training experience contributes significantly to identity formation and confidence-building among SK officials. As Tarricone et al. (2021) note, ongoing leadership training facilitates youth empowerment by enhancing decision-making and fostering resilience in the face of local governance challenges.

Finally, respondents acknowledged, with a \bar{x} of 4.69, that the mandatory training provides newly-elected SK officials with a comprehensive understanding of their roles and responsibilities, thus enabling them to serve their communities more efficiently. This aligns with the provision in the SK Reform Act to professionalize youth governance by equipping officials with operational, ethical, and technical knowledge. As emphasized by Heibel et al. (2024) in Alcantar and Segundo (2025), leadership programs can improve the decision-making abilities of officials beneficial in governing the locality they are serving.

Table 4. Extent Familiarity of the Respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of Mandatory Leadership Training

Indicators	\bar{x}	EoF
1. The anti-political dynasty provision of the SK Reform Act of 2015 prohibit individuals who are related within the second civil degree of consanguinity or affinity to any incumbent elected official in the same area to run for SK positions.	4.56	VH
2. The provision has necessary rules and regulations, along with corresponding penalties and punishment by law.	4.55	VH
3. The country guarantees equal accessto opportunities for public service and prohibits political dynasties.	4.51	VH
4. In all cases, no person who has a political dynasty relationship to the incumbent shall immediately succeed to the position of the latter.	4.50	VH
	Composite	4.53
		VH

Legend: Scale	Extent of Familiarity (EoF)
4.21 – 5.00	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)

Table 4 presents the extent of familiarity of the respondents with the Anti-Dynasty Provision of the SK Reform Act of 2015, with a composite \bar{x} of 4.53, interpreted as “Very High.” This result suggests that youth leaders are highly aware of the legal restrictions on political dynasties and the importance of ensuring fair access to youth leadership positions.

The indicator with the highest \bar{x} score of 4.56 indicates that respondents are well-informed about the provision prohibiting individuals related within the second civil degree of consanguinity or affinity to any incumbent elected official in the same area from running for SK positions. This shows that SK leaders understand how the law seeks to break the cycle of political inheritance at the grassroots level. According to Mendoza et al. (2023) political dynasties have long dominated local governance in the Philippines, and such provisions aim to disrupt these power structures to allow broader citizen participation.

The next indicator, with a \bar{x} of 4.55, reflects that respondents are aware that the anti-dynasty provision is supported by specific rules, regulations, and legal consequences. This implies that SK leaders recognize that these provisions are not just symbolic but come with enforcement mechanisms that legitimize their implementation. Research by Mendoza et al. (2019) emphasizes that clear regulatory frameworks are essential in curbing dynastic practices and reinforcing democratic accountability among elected officials.

The statement “The country guarantees equal access to opportunities for public service and prohibits political dynasties” was rated with a \bar{x} of 4.51, indicating that respondents are familiar with the broader constitutional principle behind the anti-dynasty clause. This

reflects a more nuanced understanding among youth leaders that political fairness is not only a legal issue but also a constitutional right. As noted by Emperio (2024), this principle aims to empower a wider range of citizens to participate in governance, regardless of their political affiliations or family background.

Lastly, the indicator with a \bar{x} of 4.50 highlights that respondents understand that succession by individuals related to current officeholders is restricted under this provision. This awareness helps prevent the misuse of SK positions as steppingstones for extending family political dominance. A study by Sachs-Cobbe and Douglas (2023) points out that limiting political succession among family members can foster merit-based leadership and encourage diverse representation, especially in youth councils.

Table 5. Extent Familiarity of the Respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of Creation of a Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) (n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	EoF
1. The law mandated the establishment of a Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) in every city and municipality.	4.68	VH
2. The role in LYDC involves overseeing and assessing the execution of the Local Youth Development Plan, as well as fulfilling any other mandated duties.	4.63	VH
3. The members of LYDC must be a Filipino citizen, resident of City/Municipality for at least one year, 15-30 years of age, able to read and write in Filipino and English or the local language, and has no conviction by final judgement or any crime involving moral turpitude.	4.62	VH
4. The purpose of the creation of LYDC is assisting on the planning and execution of programs and projects for the SK and Federation at all levels	4.60	VH
5. The LYDC is made up of representatives from youth and youth-serving organizations at the local, city, and provincial levels. The LYDC is led by the SK Federation President	4.58	VH
Composite	4.62	VH

Legend: Scale	Extent of Familiarity (EoF)
4.21 – 5.00	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)

Table 5 presents the extent of familiarity of the respondents with the Creation of a Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) under the SK Reform Act of 2015. The table reveals a composite \bar{x} of 4.62, interpreted as “Very High”, indicating that SK officials are deeply familiar with the structure, purpose, and legal provisions related to the LYDC. This awareness underscores the significance of participatory governance and the importance of institutional mechanisms for youth involvement.

The highest-rated statement, with a \bar{x} score of 4.68, shows that respondents are strongly aware that the law mandates the creation of a Local Youth Development Council in every city and municipality. This institutional requirement highlights the state's commitment to ensuring youth representation in policymaking. According to Chugani et al. (2021), the institutionalization of LYDCs strengthens youth engagement by providing formal avenues for participation, advocacy, and planning within local government units.

With a \bar{x} of 4.63, respondents show familiarity with the responsibilities of LYDCs in overseeing and evaluating the implementation of the Local Youth Development Plan. This suggests that youth leaders are not only aware of the council's existence but also understand their active roles in governance. Research by Torda (2024) supports this, stating that effective youth councils are vital in translating national youth agendas into localized and sustainable community programs.

A \bar{x} score of 4.62 indicates that respondents understand the eligibility requirements for LYDC membership, which include Filipino citizenship, age limits, literacy, and good moral standing. Awareness of these qualifications ensures transparency and inclusivity, reinforcing the principle that leadership opportunities should be open and merit-based. As argued by Sithole et al. (2024) young people's involvement in decision-making need to be diverse. While they can be active, some participate more than the others, especially in high level decisions, like leading the youth. It is therefore recommended to support them to participate effectively through merit-based selection. Clear criteria encourage civic-minded individuals and discourage tokenism in governance.

Another indicator, with a \bar{x} of 4.60, shows that respondents understand the LYDC's purpose in assisting the planning and execution of SK programs and projects across all levels. This reflects an appreciation for the strategic and supportive role that LYDCs play in aligning youth programs with broader goals. As discussed by Palangdao et al. (2023), the SK is tasked with creating and executing resolutions that benefit the youth and the society. Active youth participation in various sectors is encouraged as reflected in the Philippine Youth Development Plan. Likewise, the SK Chair plays an important role in local governance representing the interests of the youth in the Barangay council.

Lastly, the indicator with a \bar{x} of 4.58 suggests that respondents are aware of the composition of the LYDC, particularly that it includes youth and youth-serving organizations and is chaired by the SK Federation President. This inclusivity helps promote collaboration between different youth sectors. Amante et al. (2024) highlight that youth representation from various backgrounds ensures diverse perspectives in governance, promoting equity and effectiveness in local policymaking.

Table 6. Extent Familiarity of the Respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 in terms of Financial Independence

Indicators	\bar{x}	EoF
1. Sangguniang Kabataan funds must be recorded in financial records, simplified as prescribed by the Commission on Audit,	4.70	VH

	and subject to existing accounting and auditing laws.		
2.	Sangguniang Kabataan funds will be allocated annually and supplementally, prioritize programs promoting quality education, environmental protection, climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction, youth employment, health, gender sensitivity, sports development, and leadership training.	4.63	VH
3.	The Sangguniang Bayan or Panlungsod must review the annual budget and supplements of the Sangguniang Kabataan within 60 days, ensuring compliance with existing laws and regulations.	4.62	VH
4.	The law aimed to give SK councils a degree of financial independence by allocating 10% of the general fund of the barangay for youth development and empowerment programs.	4.59	VH
5.	The SKs shall have financial independence in their operations, disbursements and encashment of their funds, income and expenditure.	4.57	VH
		Composite	4.62
			VH

Legend: Scale	Extent of Familiarity (EoF)
4.21 – 5.00	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)

Table 6 shows the extent of familiarity of the respondents with the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2015 specifically in terms of financial independence. The composite \bar{x} of 4.62, interpreted as “Very High”, reveals that youth leaders are highly aware of the financial responsibilities, provisions, and independence granted to the SK under the law. This reflects their understanding of the legal and procedural aspects of budget management, as well as their accountability as stewards of public funds.

Respondents demonstrated strong familiarity with the legal requirement that SK funds must be properly recorded, simplified under Commission on Audit guidelines, and follow national accounting and auditing laws, which earned the highest \bar{x} score of 4.70. This suggests that youth leaders understand the need for transparency and adherence to financial standards in managing public funds. According to Erlina et al. (2023), promoting fiscal responsibility among SK officials and Barangay Officials is link to good governance and competence. Citing the work of Caldo (2015 in Erlina et al., 2023) it was argued that SK officials become confident in the performance of their duties and function. The study also pointed out that transparency should be observed through public disclosure, as proper financial reporting public trust.

The indicator with a \bar{x} of 4.63 shows that respondents are aware that SK funds must prioritize youth-centered programs such as education, environmental protection, climate resilience, health, gender sensitivity, employment, and leadership training. This indicates an understanding that the use of SK funds should be aligned with national development goals and youth welfare. This result is similar to the findings of Pasicaran-Escleto et al. (2024), which argues that SK officials should perceived themselves to be responsible in addressing the issues raised by their constituents. Being the voice of the youth includes

deeper commitment of providing meaningful service through mobilizing resources to implement programs beneficial to the youth.

A \bar{x} of 4.62 reflects familiarity with the requirement for the Sangguniang Bayan or Panlungsod to review SK budgets within 60 days to ensure legal compliance. This awareness reveals that SK officials recognize the importance of institutional checks and balances in budget execution. As noted by Castillo and Santiago (2021), local government oversight mechanisms are crucial in safeguarding funds from mismanagement while still allowing youth councils to operate with autonomy.

The data also shows that respondents are familiar with the law’s intent to allocate 10% of the barangay’s general fund to SK for youth empowerment programs, reflected in a \bar{x} of 4.59. This reflects understanding of the provision that guarantees SKs a fixed budget source for their initiatives.

Lastly, with a \bar{x} of 4.57, respondents understand that SKs are granted autonomy in handling their disbursements, encashments, and expenditures. This financial freedom allows SKs to function independently while being held accountable for the use of public funds.

Table 7. Extent to which the SK Reform Act Manifest the Leadership Perspectives of the Respondents in terms of Decision-Making and Problem Solving (n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoM
1. I believe that the SK Reform Act has equipped me with critical thinking and decision-making skills necessary for effective governance.	4.62	SA	VH
2. The leadership training mandated by the reform has improved my problem-solving strategies in addressing youth concerns.	4.59	SA	VH
3. The SK Reform Act has enhanced my ability to analyze problems and make informed decisions in governance.	4.58	SA	VH
4. The reforms have provided me with the practical skills for evaluating different solutions to community issues	4.57	SA	VH
5. I feel more confident in my ability to make sound decisions under pressure since the implementation of the SK Reform Act.	4.55	SA	VH
Composite	4.58	SA	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Manifestations (EoM)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 7 presents the extent to which the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2015 manifests in the leadership perspectives of respondents, particularly in terms of decision-making and problem-solving. The data reveals a composite \bar{x} of 4.58, interpreted as “Very

High”, indicating that the youth respondents strongly agree that the SK Reform Act has significantly shaped their leadership capacities, especially in handling issues and making informed decisions in governance.

The highest-rated statement, with a \bar{x} of 4.62, reflects that respondents believe the SK Reform Act has equipped them with critical thinking and decision-making skills necessary for effective governance. This suggests a strong link between policy-driven training and actual improvements in cognitive leadership functions. In line with this, Flores et al. (2022) also contend that positive effect of the SK Reform Act especially in providing young leaders with the needed skills in doing their job. However, the authors also noted the challenges SK officials faced like that of the lack of skills in submitting viable plans.

Another highly rated item ($\bar{x} = 4.59$) suggests that respondents perceive the mandatory leadership training as a key contributor to enhancing their problem-solving strategies in addressing youth concerns. This indicates that the reform not only outlines structural changes but also provides direct capacity-building mechanisms that translate into applied governance practices.

Respondents also agreed ($\bar{x} = 4.58$) that the SK Reform Act has enhanced their ability to analyze problems and make informed decisions in governance, pointing to a deeper understanding of analytical frameworks used in local policy-making. This aligns with findings by Reguindin (2023), who found that structured leadership training increases analytical competencies among young political leaders, empowering them to implement evidence-based decisions.

Furthermore, a \bar{x} of 4.57 highlights respondents’ agreement that the reforms have provided practical skills in evaluating solutions to community issues. This implies that SK officials are not only aware of different policy options but can assess them critically.

Lastly, the indicator on confidence in making sound decisions under pressure, with a \bar{x} of 4.55, demonstrates that youth leaders have become more resilient and decisive in high-stress situations since the implementation of the reform Calawa et al. (2023) support this view, stating that confidence in leadership emerges from both theoretical knowledge and field experience—two aspects emphasized in the SK Reform Act’s training modules.

Table 8. Extent to which the SK Reform Act Manifest the Leadership Perspectives of the Respondents in terms of Community Engagement (n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoM
1. The community views SK leaders more positively since the implementation of the reform.	4.70	SA	VH
2. The SK Reform Act has increased my involvement in community development projects.	4.61	SA	VH
3. The SK Reform Act has improved the collaboration between the SK and other local government units.	4.61	SA	VH
4. I feel that the reform has made it easier to engage with and	4.55	SA	VH

mobilize the youth in my community.

5. The reforms have allowed me to initiate more impactful projects in my barangay. 4.52 SA VH

			Composite	4.60	SA	VH
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Manifestations (EoM)				
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)				
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)				
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)				
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)				
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)				

Table 8 shows the extent to which the SK Reform Act of 2015 manifests the leadership perspectives of the respondents in terms of community engagement. With a composite \bar{x} of 4.60, interpreted as “Very High”, the data indicates that the respondents strongly agree that the reform has significantly improved their involvement and leadership in their communities.

The highest-rated item, with a \bar{x} of 4.70, highlights that the community views SK leaders more positively since the implementation of the reform. This suggests that the structural and ethical reforms introduced by the SK Reform Act—such as anti-dynasty provisions and mandatory leadership training—have contributed to building public trust. According to Flores et al. (2022), improving youth leadership credibility through policy reform enhances the public’s perception of young leaders and encourages greater community support for youth-led initiatives.

Two indicators both scored a high \bar{x} of 4.61, reflecting that respondents strongly agree that their involvement in community development projects and collaboration between the SK and other local government units have improved. These findings point to enhanced inter-agency coordination and deeper grassroots involvement in governance.

Respondents also expressed agreement ($\bar{x} = 4.55$) that the reform has made it easier to engage with and mobilize the youth in their community. This underscores the effectiveness of the SK in acting as a bridge between local government and the youth sector. Research by Motte-Muñoz (2020) suggests that when youth leaders are empowered through policy, they become more capable of mobilizing peer support and organizing collective action.

Lastly, a \bar{x} of 4.52 shows that the reforms have allowed respondents to initiate more impactful projects in their barangay, demonstrating that the structural autonomy and clearer funding mechanisms provided by the SK Reform Act are enabling youth leaders to implement initiatives that address real community needs.

Table 9. Extent to which the SK Reform Act Manifest the Leadership Perspectives of the Respondents in terms of Perception of Perception of Roles and Responsibilities(n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoM
1. The increased accountability measures have made me more responsible in fulfilling my duties.	4.73	SA	VH
2. The SK Reform Act of 2015 clearly defines my roles and responsibilities as an SK leader.	4.58	SA	VH
3. I believe that my role as an SK leader is more significant after the reform.	4.54	SA	VH
4. I feel empowered to make decisions that benefit my community under the reformed SK system.	4.52	SA	VH
5. The anti-political dynasty provision of the reform has positively influenced my perception of my role.	4.52	SA	VH
Composite	4.58	SA	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Manifestations (EoM)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 9 presents the extent to which the SK Reform Act of 2015 manifests the leadership perspectives of the respondents in terms of their perception of roles and responsibilities. With a composite \bar{x} of 4.58, interpreted as “Very High”, the data indicates that the respondents strongly agree that the reform has positively influenced how they understand and fulfill their roles as youth leaders.

The highest \bar{x} score of 4.73 was given to the statement that “the increased accountability measures have made me more responsible in fulfilling my duties.” This finding affirms that the reform’s emphasis on transparency, ethical conduct, and oversight mechanisms has led to a stronger sense of responsibility among SK officials. According to Garst et al. (2023), increased accountability in youth governance results in greater diligence and ethical behavior among elected youth leaders, fostering more credible leadership.

With a \bar{x} of 4.58, respondents also strongly agree that the SK Reform Act clearly defines their roles and responsibilities. This highlights the effectiveness of the reform in eliminating ambiguity and providing structured guidance for SK officials.

Furthermore, respondents reported a strong sense of purpose in their leadership positions, with a \bar{x} of 4.54 indicating agreement that their role as SK leaders became more significant after the reform. This aligns with the reform’s intent to elevate the capacity and relevance of the SK in local governance.

Two items received a \bar{x} score of 4.52, reflecting that respondents feel empowered to make decisions that benefit their communities and that the anti-political dynasty provision has positively shaped their perception of their role. These indicators show that the reform not

only enabled a culture of independent leadership but also instilled a more inclusive and principled approach to governance.

Table 10. Extent to which the SK Reform Act Manifest the Leadership Perspectives of the Respondents in terms of Motivation and Commitment (n=267)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoM
1. The SK Reform Act has motivated me to continue serving in local governance.	4.57	SA	VH
2. I would recommend others to join the SK because of the positive changes brought by the reform.	4.57	SA	VH
3. I feel that the SK system is now more supportive of young leaders' ambitions.	4.55	SA	VH
4. I am more committed to my role as an SK leader because of the reforms.	4.51	SA	VH
5. The reforms have encouraged me to pursue a career in public service.	4.46	SA	VH
Composite	4.58	SA	VH

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Manifestations (EoM)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 10 presents the extent to which the SK Reform Act of 2015 manifests the leadership perspectives of the respondents in terms of their motivation and commitment to youth governance. The composite \bar{x} score of 4.58, interpreted as “Very High,” suggests that respondents strongly agree that the reform has significantly influenced their dedication to public service and leadership within the SK.

Two items received the highest \bar{x} scores of 4.57: (1) “The SK Reform Act has motivated me to continue serving in local governance” and (2) “I would recommend others to join the SK because of the positive changes brought by the reform.” These scores reflect that the reforms have reignited passion and purpose among youth leaders, positioning the SK as a more credible and fulfilling platform for civic engagement.

The item “I feel that the SK system is now more supportive of young leaders' ambitions” scored 4.55, indicating that respondents perceive the current system as one that nurtures and encourages the aspirations of youth in governance.

Respondents also expressed high commitment to their current role, with a \bar{x} of 4.51 for the statement “I am more committed to my role as an SK leader because of the reforms.” This implies that the structural improvements made under the reform — such as mandatory training, clearer accountability, and financial autonomy — have strengthened leaders' sense of duty and ownership of their roles.

The statement “The reforms have encouraged me to pursue a career in public service” received a \bar{x} of 4.46, the lowest among the five, but still within the “Very High” range. This is a promising sign that the reformed SK is not only fulfilling its mandate to empower youth in governance but is also inspiring long-term civic participation and leadership careers.

Table 11. Relationship between the Extent of Familiarity of the Respondents with the SK Reform Act of 2015 and the Extent of Its Manifestations in Their Leadership Perspectives

<i>Overall Familiarity and...</i>	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Decision-Making and Problem Solving	0.675	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Community Engagement	0.720	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Perception of Roles and Responsibilities	0.768	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Motivation and Commitment	0.728	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation (r_s) at 0.05 Level of Significance; n=267

Table 11 presents the relationship between the respondents' extent of familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015 and the extent of its manifestations in their leadership perspectives. The results indicate significant positive correlations across all four leadership domains: Decision-Making and Problem Solving ($r_s = 0.675$, $p < .001$), Community Engagement ($r_s = 0.720$, $p < .001$), Perception of Roles and Responsibilities ($r_s = 0.768$, $p < .001$), and Motivation and Commitment ($r_s = 0.728$, $p < .001$). Since all p-values are below the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected for each indicator. This suggests that the more familiar the respondents are with the SK Reform Act, the more these leadership qualities are manifested. The findings emphasize the importance of awareness and understanding of the SK Reform Act in shaping youth leaders' behavior and orientation in leadership roles.

These results imply that greater awareness and understanding of the provisions, principles, and goals of the SK Reform Act are associated with higher levels of demonstrated leadership behaviors. In particular, respondents who are more knowledgeable about the Act report stronger capabilities in decision-making, greater involvement in community development, clearer recognition of their leadership roles, and deeper motivation to serve. This confirms that legal literacy and policy orientation are crucial for the empowerment of youth leaders.

The findings are supported by Brady et al. (2020), who emphasized that youth leaders who are informed about governance frameworks are more confident in initiating policies and managing programs. The same study noted that when youth leaders clearly understand the mandates of the SK Reform Act, they are better able to operationalize their duties effectively and ethically.

Table 12. Relationship between the Profile of the Respondents and Their Extent of Familiarity of the SK Reform Act of 2015

<i>Overall Familiarity and...</i>	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
	r_{pbi}			
Sex	0.015	0.809	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
	r_s			
Age	0.172	0.005	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.159	0.009	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Number of Mandatory Trainings	0.055	0.374	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
Length of Service in SK	0.038	0.539	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant

Point-Biserial Correlation (r_{pbi}) and Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation (r_s) at 0.05 Level of Significance; n=267

Table 12 explores the relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their extent of familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015. The results show that age ($r_s = 0.172$, $p = 0.005$) and educational attainment ($r_s = 0.159$, $p = 0.009$) have significant positive relationships with familiarity, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{o2}) for these two variables. This means that older and more educated respondents tend to be more familiar with the provisions of the SK Reform Act. However, sex ($r_{pbi} = 0.015$, $p = 0.809$), number of mandatory trainings ($r_s = 0.055$, $p = 0.374$), and length of service in SK ($r_s = 0.038$, $p = 0.539$) did not yield significant relationships, hence the null hypothesis is not rejected for these factors. These results signify that demographic attribute like age and education play a more substantial role in shaping familiarity with policy content than experience-based factors like trainings or service length.

This result is supported by the findings of Erikson (1968) in his theory of psychosocial development, which suggests that as individuals age, they accumulate experiences and develop cognitive maturity, enabling them to engage more meaningfully with complex social structures such as governance and policy. In the context of youth leadership, age is often linked with increased awareness of civic duties and legal mandates. Similarly, Chen and Madni (2024) also found that higher educational levels are associated with greater political education and awareness and legal literacy among young people, as education provides access to structured knowledge and promotes critical thinking.

Table 13. Relationship between the respondents' profile and the extent of the manifestations of their leadership perspectives.

<i>Overall Manifestations of Leadership Perspective and...</i>	Comp.	p-value	Decision	Remark
	r_{pbi}			
Sex	0.091	0.140	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
	r_s			
Age	0.207	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.336	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Number of Mandatory Trainings	0.106	0.085	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
Length of Service in SK	0.075	0.223	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant

Point-Biserial Correlation (r_{pbi}) and Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation (r_s) at 0.05 Level of Significance; n=267

Table 13 examines the relationship between the respondents' profile and the extent of the manifestations of their leadership perspectives. Educational attainment ($r_s = 0.336$, $p < .001$) and age ($r_s = 0.207$, $p < .001$) show significant positive relationships with leadership manifestation, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for both variables. This implies that older and more educated youth leaders demonstrate stronger leadership traits. Meanwhile, no significant relationships were found for sex ($r_{pbi} = 0.091$, $p = 0.140$), number of mandatory trainings ($r_s = 0.106$, $p = 0.085$), and length of service in SK ($r_s = 0.075$, $p = 0.223$), with the null hypothesis being retained. These findings highlight that personal maturity and formal education are more influential in developing leadership perspectives than mere participation in trainings or years of service.

These results align with the study of Leong and Fischer (2011), which emphasized that age and education are associated with increased self-awareness, improved decision-making, and enhanced civic responsibility, all of which contribute to stronger leadership capacities. As individuals age and attain higher levels of education, they are more likely to be exposed to complex social, political, and organizational issues, thereby improving their leadership maturity and competencies.

On the other hand, sex ($r_{pbi} = 0.091$, $p = 0.140$), a wide range of compulsory training ($r_s = 0.106$, $p = \text{zero}.5$), and the duration of the SK ($r_s = 0.1/2$, $p = 0.223$) did reduce, stored for storage with zero mortgage. variable.

This is in line with the findings of Akira et al. (2024), which claimed that implementing youth-focused programs, lack of awareness, and time constraints were some of the challenges faced by SK officials. In addition, Erlina et al. (2023) found that young people who have interaction in leading roles passively or without continuous learning generally have a plateau in the phases of the development, regardless of their career. Thus, they differ in reflection, mentoring, or continuous study, which have a limited impact on the boom of administration.

Conclusions

The findings of this study emphasize that members of Generation Z Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) are not only socially aware but also demonstrate strong leadership capabilities. Their roles and perspectives are notably shaped by their high level of familiarity with the SK Reform Act of 2015, indicating that recent reforms have been effective in empowering youth leaders through clear guidelines, structured responsibilities, and accountability mechanisms. These reforms appear to translate into concrete improvements in governance capacity, as seen in the respondents' high ratings in leadership dimensions such as decision-making, community engagement, and motivation.

Moreover, the results affirm that awareness and understanding of relevant policies—particularly those that define the roles, limitations, and responsibilities of youth leaders—are critical in shaping leadership behavior. Youth leaders who are more informed about the provisions of the SK Reform Act are significantly more likely to display effective

leadership qualities. This supports the notion that their knowledge of the law likely sharpened their understanding of leadership principles, deepened their civic consciousness, empowered their decision-making, and strengthened their motivation — making them socially aware and strong in leadership.

Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of age and educational attainment as primary contributors to civic competence and leadership effectiveness. As youth leaders grow older and advance in their formal education, they tend to exhibit a more mature and refined approach to leadership. This is likely due to increased exposure to civic institutions, critical thinking development, and practical learning experiences, all of which contribute to the shaping of a well-rounded public servant. In contrast, variables such as sex/gender, length of service, and the number of trainings attended were found to have no significant influence, the lack of significant influence from trainings suggests that training quantity alone does not guarantee meaningful leadership growth. Without high-quality, relevant, experiential, and well-integrated learning opportunities, trainings may fail to foster the critical civic competence and leadership effectiveness needed for genuine youth participation in governance.

Ultimately, these insights point to a need for continued investment in youth policy education, civic training, and leadership development initiatives that are grounded in both legal literacy and academic support. By focusing on these key areas, the Philippines can better ensure that its future leaders are not only inspired but also equipped to lead with knowledge, integrity, and purpose.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure high standards of ethical research, it was essential to consider ethical factors. Participants were first informed about the study's purpose and conditions, with their informed consent gathered through a disclosure statement. It was highlighted that they could withdraw from the study at any point without feeling worried or apprehensive. Additionally, strict confidentiality measures were implemented to safeguard the privacy of shared information.

The study also aimed to reduce any jeopardy to the participants. Throughout the process, the researcher maintained a non-judgmental attitude to avoid any criticism.

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